

Stretch(Scale) Transformations and Quantum to Classical Transition

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In (1), it is suggested that classical phase space distributions emerge from the quantum Wigner(x,p) distribution in a certain limit which (1) calls a high entropy limit. This limit is introduced through a stretch transformation. For classical phase space variables, x,p, a stretch transformation obeys: $\langle T(x^m p^n) \rangle = \sqrt{b}^{m+n} \langle x^m p^n \rangle$, where b is a parameter. This stretch transformation is applied to the semi-classical Wigner distribution and it is shown that it only has positive values in the $b \gg 1$ limit. (Below this limit, it may be positive or negative.) They also show that W evolves according to classical mechanics, $dW(x,p)/dt \approx \{H, W\}$, where $\{ \}$ are Poisson brackets.

In this note, we try to consider scaling (like stretching) in special relativity and compare it with wavelengths and periods (quantum) which appear in this scenario as described in (2). We begin with the Lorentz invariant: $x'^2 - t'^2 = x^2 - t^2$ (c=1). Here (0,t) describe a particle with rest mass at rest at x=0. We note that: $t' = \gamma(v)t$ and $x' = \gamma(v)v t$, where $\gamma(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and that one may scale $t \rightarrow bt$. This leads to:

$b(x' \text{ unscaled}) - b(t' \text{ unscaled}) = -t' b$. One may divide by t' (unscaled) in which case dividing by t' unscaled yields (and multiplying by appropriate functions of v) yields:

$b(x' \text{ unscaled}) / b(t' \text{ unscaled}) = -t' b / (t' \text{ unscaled})$ because $(x'/t') \text{ unscaled} = v$ and $(x'/t') \text{ scaled} = v$. This is equivalent to: $b(x' \gamma(v)v \text{ unscaled}) - b(t' \gamma(v)) = -t' m_0$. Thus, one sees a scaling in the rest frame of t and a scaling of x' and p' by the same b in the moving frame.

In (2), we showed that the $x'^2 - t'^2 = t^2$ invariant may be written as: $x' \gamma(v)v - \gamma(v)t = t$ suggesting that for a given t_1' , x_1' solution, $x_1' + \text{constant}/(\gamma v)$ and $t_1' + \text{constant}/\gamma$ are also solutions suggesting the existence of a quantum wavelength and period. Given that (x,t)=(0,0) Lorentz transforms to (0,0), x', t' also represent intervals. $\gamma(v)v$ remains unchanged under the $t \rightarrow bt$ transformation so the shift is unchanged. If $\text{constant}/(\gamma v)$ and $\text{constant}/\gamma$ are of the order of an interval $x' \rightarrow 0$, $t' \rightarrow 0$, then scaling $x' \rightarrow bx'$, for $b \gg 1$, means that many $\text{constant}/(\gamma v)$'s fit inside the interval. If $x' \rightarrow 0$ is considered a small interval classically, then the degeneracy represented by $\text{constant}/(\gamma v)$ is not really seen and one does not have quantum effects, we argue.

Stretching Transformation of (1)

In (1), a classical stretching transformation T is defined by:

$$T(x,p) \rightarrow (\sqrt{b} x, \sqrt{b} p) \quad \text{where } b \text{ is parameter from } 1 \text{ to infinite } ((1))$$

In particular then, $\langle T(x^m p^n) \rangle = \sqrt{b}^{m+n} \langle x^m p^n \rangle$ ((2)).

The approach of (1) is to stretch transform the semiclassical Wigner distribution (3). The Wigner distribution was created historically so as to link the quantum wavefunction to a classical spatial probability distribution in x-p phase space. It is given by (3):

$$\text{Wigner}(x, p) = 1 / (3.14 \hbar) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} W^*(x+y) W(x-y) \exp(i2py/\hbar) dy \quad (4)$$

The issue is that $\text{Wigner}(x,p)$ may be negative in some cases, which is not physical.

The authors of (1) show that a stretch transformation leads to the case of $b \gg 1$ ensuring that $\text{Wigner}(x,p)$ is always positive (i.e. represents a classical probability distribution in phase space). They also show that:

$$d/dt \text{Wigner}(x,p) \approx \{H, \text{Wigner}(x,p)\} \quad (5) \quad \text{Here } \{ \} \text{ are the Poisson brackets}$$

Thus, (1) argues that in the large entropy limit (i.e. large stretching parameter b), quantum mechanics becomes classical statistical mechanics, i.e. leads to the $\text{Wigner}(x,p)$ describing a classical probability distribution in phase space $x-p$.

Details of this calculator are explicitly provided in (1) and so are not repeated here. The purpose of this note is to see if there is another way to consider this stretching or scaling transformation and its relation to quantum mechanics becoming classical.

Special Relativistic Considerations

We begin with the Lorentz invariant:

$$X'x' - t't' = 00 - tt \quad (c=1) \quad ((6))$$

Here one has a particle at rest on the RHS so $x=0$. One also has:

$$x' = v g(v) t \quad \text{and} \quad t' = g(v) t \quad \text{where} \quad g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((7))$$

We consider a scale transformation of: $t \rightarrow bt$ ((8)) where $b > 1$

$$\text{Then } ((6)) \text{ becomes: } bb(x' x'/t') \text{ unscaled} - bb(t' \text{ unscaled}) = -bb(tt/t') \text{ unscaled} \quad ((9))$$

If one multiplies $x'/t' = v$ by $m_0 g(v)$ on e has momentum, so then:

$$b(x' p') \text{ unscaled} - b m_0 g(v) (t' \text{ unscaled}) = -b m_0 (t) \quad ((10))$$

Thus, one sees that x', t', t scale and p', E' and m_0 do not. One can, however, multiply by b so as to make it appear as if p', E', m_0' scale, but physically they do not. In the classical limit, one is really concerned with dx and dp values and so these scale, but a given momentum is the same regardless what external clock or ruler intervals one uses.

Next, we reconsider ((6)) as in (2) and linearize it:

$$X' v g - t' g = - t \quad ((11))$$

((11)) implies that if x_1' and t_1' are solutions then so are:

$$X' = x_1' + \text{constant}/(gv) \quad \text{and} \quad t' = t_1' + \text{constant}/g \quad ((12))$$

In other words, quantum wavelengths and periods appear which are unchanged by scaling. (The constant is \hbar/m_0) As a result, if the wavelength and period in ((12)) are of the order of the system size, then they are important, i.e. quantum effects are essential. One may note that $(0,0)=(x,t)$ transforms to $(0,0)$, so x and t may be considered as intervals from the origin.

Under the scale transformation $t \rightarrow bt$ which scales phase space $x' \rightarrow bx'$ and $p' \rightarrow bp'$, as in the stretch transformation of (1), the wavelength and period do not scale, but remain as:

$$\text{constant}/(gv) \quad \text{for } x' \quad \text{and} \quad \text{constant}/g \quad \text{for } t'$$

Thus, one may simply scale x' to create an interval in x for which there are numerous $\text{constant}/(gv)$ units, for a given $\text{constant}=\hbar/m_0$. In such a case, the wavelength is obscured, i.e. there are no quantum effects.

We suggest that this form of scaling is similar to that presented in (1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that (1) considers a stretching transformation $T(x,p) \rightarrow (\sqrt{b}x, \sqrt{b}p)$ where b is a parameter >1 and applies it to the Wigner distribution (x,p) which is supposed to map a quantum wavefunction to a classical x,p distribution. The problem is that the Wigner (x,p) function can be negative in some cases, making it unphysical in these situations. The authors of (1) show that if one applies the stretch transformation to Wigner (x,p) , then for $b \gg 1$, Wigner (x,p) is guaranteed to be positive and to follow $d/dt \text{ Wigner}(x,p) \approx \{ H, \text{ Wigner}(x,p) \}$ where $\{ \}$ are the Poisson brackets.

We consider transitioning from quantum to classical mechanics in a different way, albeit one which uses a scaling transformation. We consider the free particle described by special relativity and the Lorentz invariant: $x'^2 - t'^2 = t^2$ ($c=1$). We then scale $t \rightarrow bt$ and show that one has:

$$Bb(x' p') \text{ unscaled} - bb(t' E') \text{ unscaled} = -bb \text{ mot unscaled}$$

Thus, one scales x', p' . Given that $(x,t)=(0,0)$ maps to $(0,0)$ under a Lorentz transformation, x', t' also represent intervals from the origin.

We showed in (2) that $x'^2 - t'^2 = -t^2$ may be written as: $x' = \gamma(v)g t'$ and $t' = \gamma(v)t$ so if x_1' and t_1' satisfy this equation, so do: $x' = x_1' + \text{constant}/(\gamma(v)g)$ and $t' = t_1' + \text{constant}/(\gamma(v)g)$. Here $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$. The shifted x' and t' pieces do not change under a scale transformation. This means that even though one has bp' and bE_p in the equation above, $x' = x_1' + \hbar/(\gamma(v)g)$ and $t' = t_1' + \hbar/(\gamma(v)g)$ are solutions even if x', x_1' and t', t_1' scale. In other words, consider a free particle with a wavelength \hbar/p . Consider a dx of the order of this wavelength. In such a case, one sees the single wavelength. If one considers a very large dx (which is the classical citation), then many wavelengths fit inside and one does not really notice the wavelength.

Thus, if one has x' and t' prime intervals for which the shifts are sizable, one has quantum effects. A scale transformation, $t \rightarrow bt$, however, changes these x', t' intervals without changing the wavelength or period and so if an x' and t' interval are considered small classically (after the scaling $t \rightarrow bt$), then the effects of the degeneracies, i.e. wavelength and period, are not resolved and it is as if they are not present.

References

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